

Spider Streetview: Jumping spiders in a maze learn to employ different navigational strategies in dependence of preceding visual exploration from a bird's eye view

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2014

Masterthesis

of the Master's degree course Biology
at the University of Hamburg, Germany

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... Anansi was so annoyed with his failed attempts to climb the tree and the realization that his child was right, that he let the pot, he selfishly had wanted to keep for himself, slip.

It smashed and all the wisdom on the inside fell out.

Just at this moment a storm arrived and the rain washed all the wisdom into the stream. It was taken out to the sea and spread all around the world, so that there is now a little of it in everyone.

<based on the African fairy tale about the spider-god Anansi and the dispersal of wisdom>

Dedication:

To my Father, for whom I hereby realize, what he undeservingly never had the confidence to realize for himself.

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Summary (abstract)

The actively hunting lifestyle of jumping spiders (i.e. they do not build webs to capture prey but leave their retreat to go foraging) requires a specialization of cognitive abilities and sensory modalities, of which the latter exemplary manifests in these animals as acute, stereoscopic eye-vision. It was already shown, that jumping spiders can make detours to reach prey in sight, and make choices based on former experiences. Hence, visual observation and memorization of environmental cues might be important for saving energy, otherwise spent on motor-activity for correcting wrong navigational choices. We investigated the influence of preceding visual exploration on the performance of differently reared jumping spiders (*Marpissa muscosa*) presented to a four-armed maze. The maze was equipped with a yellow colored block as associative stimulus and a food reward in one corner. We then covered the maze with transparent glass. On 7 consecutive days, half of the spiders were allowed to inspect the maze from above (i.e. through the glass panel) for 20 minutes, while the other half had their view blocked. Both groups were then put in the maze for 1 hour in which they had the opportunity to search for the reward. After 4 days, reversal learning was induced by changing the location of reward. We recorded the numbers of correct choices (i.e. going straight to the rewarded corner) and the general explorative behavior of spiders to investigate the influence of upbringing and visual exploration on the spiders' performance. Generalized linear mixed models were derived from the data to describe the spiders' learning-behavior in the actually conducted reversal trial and a hypothetical trial without reversal, where the reward-locations were assumed to not have changed after day 4. It is shown, that visual exploration, motivation and number of trials have an effect on the spiders' performance as a chance of success, which was defined by a correct first choice of the corner containing the reward.

Introduction

The environment a mobile animal navigates every day, offers diverse challenges. Some of the factors contributing to those challenges change regularly, some do so only once, and others stay the same over a whole lifetime. Moving about in this environment (locomotion) can be costly, depending on the energy expenditure that is necessary to cover a certain distance. As an example, ungulates employ different strategies for climbing a slope if it is either very steep or only gently inclined (Robbins, 1993). For this reason, it is an advantage to know the properties of an area, especially one's home range: To save energy through taking shortcuts, to avoid obstacles and not getting lost on the way to a target location. The estimation of one's position in respect to the known world is fundamental to navigation, which is defined as a process of determining and maintaining a trajectory from one place to another (Gallistel, 1990).

The processes that enable such intentional navigational behavior in turn, are learning and the formation of memories. An animal explores its environment, usually in "episodes of feverish activity" (Poucet and Herrmann, 2001), which can mean it moves repeatedly from place to place and investigates some of them more closely. The associated assumption is, the animal then integrates the sensory input or information it gathers from such activity, to recall it for orientation on later occasions, perhaps in the shape of mental representation, a so called "cognitive map". The reliability of this memory can be reinforced by making the same or a very similar experience again; According to the Rescorla-Wagner Theory (Anderson, 2000) the strength of association between a conditioned and an unconditioned stimulus increases with repeated exposures. The popular notion of regular repetition being a key-factor for learning (i.e. establishing stable associations between memories) is backed up by findings all across the animal kingdom: Vertebrates, including amphibians and reptiles, and also arthropods like bees or butterflies are well known to behave flexible, as if they have memories of some preceding event or previously explored environment and can put them into context (summarized and reviewed in Gould, 2002 and Capaldi et al., 1999, several examples also mentioned in Pearce, 2008). Anderson (2000) sums it up as follows: "Learning refers to the process of adaption of behavior to experience, and memory refers to the permanent records that underlie this adaption."

An environment is subject to changes, so the associations between stimuli it offers can change over time as well. Therefore it might be adaptively advantageous to an animal if it can respond quickly to unpredictable changes in its environment and form new associations. As those associations can be reversed in comparison to the former association, this especially flexible type of learning is called "reversal learning" (Menzel, 1969).

So if an animal explores, it learns the associations between certain stimuli that are presented by its environment and adapts its future navigation-behavior according to that information. There are different types of information an environment itself offers and that can be used by an animal for orientation:

- 1) Vectors in the euclidian sense have a source point, a length and direction. Vectors describe the spatial relations between objects, or between a mobile agent (the animal) and a target the agents wants to arrive at. Because an animal can change its place and direction, a personal reference vector is needed to indicate a change of bearing. From an egocentric perspective, it often is compared to the former heading of the agent after a turn; From an allocentric (not referring to the agent itself, global) perspective, an arbitrary, conceptual reference vector is needed to describe the bearings separate

features of the landscapes share between them (Klatzky, 1998). Animals use vectors for “path integration” or “dead reckoning”, which enables them to travel long distances without external cues but with minimal course deviation (e.g Reznikova, 2007). This achieved by constant feedback from the sensori-motor complex during movement (Propioception) and its memory-integration for an estimation of travelled distance and time by recalling previous movements (Seyfarth et al., 1982).

2) Topography describes the terrain in terms of height, the accessibility of places (a mountain range confines movement between adjacent plains) and also unique features like conspicuous landmarks. Landmarks and beacons, which are landmarks that indicate the proximity of a chosen goal location to an agent, also play an important role in animal navigation. Bigger landmarks, such as mountains or lakes can provide an agent with a general direction for travelling and smaller landmarks such as a specific geometric arrangement of trees or stones provide means for homing in on a specific, locally bounded target. As an example, digger wasps, *Philanthus triangulum*, are known to search for the entrance of their nest in the wrong place, if the local cues (consisting of items such a pine cones or pebbles, including their geometric relations) are displaced by a human experimenter (Tinbergen and Kruyt, 1938).

3) Local conditions and their stochastic patterns or cycles, like lighting conditions, dampness, temperature, food abundance and hazards like predators or unstable ground.

The term “cognitive map” itself is highly controversial (Reznikova, 2007): On one hand, mapping and navigation behavior does not necessarily require cognitive abilities or involve learning; On the other, the building and usage of an abstract representation like a ‘birds’ eye view’, could very well employ simple, cognitively not so demanding mechanisms (An example for different navigation mechanisms not being mutually exclusive is given by Cheng et al., 2009, who studied the desert ant *Melophorus bagoti*). The accurate navigational abilities of arthropods, mostly bees and ants, were thoroughly reviewed (Gallistel, 1998), but to demonstrate the cognitive map-controversy, special emphasis can be put on Menzel and Wehner (1990). An experienced bee-researcher, Menzel (1969; 1993; 1996; 1999; 1998) held the case for bees having a map-like spatial memory (2005), but Wehner (1996; 1999; 1990; 1990) argued, that a global spatial representation is not necessary to achieve the same navigational performance. Apparently, the idea of a decentralized memory that works with large scale vector integration (Cruse and Wehner, 2011) convinced Menzel (2012) to study bees navigation and homing behavior from a slightly different perspective, free from the burden of having to define a “cognitive map” conclusively, but not dropping the idea of a map-like organized memory completely. The term is still applicable as a part of a cognitive system in the sense of Cruse and Wehner; 2011), namely that it “allows for exploitation of memory elements independently of the context these elements have been acquired”, not only in spatial navigation but problem solving in general.

As automation and security technology permeates more and more domains of daily life, it is a legitimate concern, that it is not only easy to operate by the human, but also responding “intelligently” to the input of its environment, just like an animal does. This is already common in some simple service robots, like the ones that are used in households for vacuum-cleaning. It becomes even more crucial for autonomous robots that are considered to be built for rescue-missions (Tadokoro, 2009) in changing, and possibly dangerous terrain. Advanced technology is expensive to develop, build and maintain, so it is not surprising that scientists in those fields look for uncomplicated and reliable solutions inspired by nature.

R. Wehner, who is already mentioned above, helped to conduct successful experiments with robots employing navigational strategies comparable to ants (Lambrinos et al., 2000). In contrast to the aforementioned wheeled machine, multi-legged robots, that are not restricted to a definite dorsal-

ventral axis, like “Asterisk” from the University of Osaka, are very good in safely maneuvering not only the ground and slopes, but also climbing obstacles like stairs and even vertical nets (Bidaud and Amar, 2002), like a spider.

The similarity is on purpose, as the locomotion of spiders posed as a model for this robot. Like bees, spiders navigate a 3 dimensional environment, but they do so on foot and not by flying, which is challenging for orientation, i.e. the distinction between the directions surfaces are pointing to becomes more important, as a change in perspective or alignment changes the view or “snapshot” of how the environmental features are related to each other. A series of such “snapshots”, containing landmarks or beacons and their spatial relations, is proposed to be the memory element that guides insect navigation along a route (Collett and Collett, 2002).

Spiders, with about 40,000 known species, show a high diversity in lifestyles, but probably all of them have to remember the location of stored prey, nests or prospective mates on a daily basis. For wandering spiders (as opposed to web-building spiders), that behave as central place foragers (Herberstein, 2011), the reliable formation of spatial associations is crucial for navigating the path between foraging sites and a familiar shelter. These actively hunting species, like wolf (Lycosidae) and jumping spiders (Salticidae), mainly rely on their acute sense of vision, which is expressed in both families as an enlarged pair of median eyes (Foelix, 2010). This simplifies a sensible trial-design for a human researcher, as many spiders can be studied and experimentally manipulated either in the field or the laboratory.

Jumping spiders in particular are known for their remarkable visual acuity. The spatial resolution of their camera-type eyes exceeds even bees’ compound eyes (Land, 1985), so they were chosen for many studies regarding learning and navigation in spiders. It was shown, that Salticidae can learn the avoidance of distasteful prey by attending to environmental cues (Skow and Jakob, 2006); Use visually distinct beacons to find an already known hiding place (Höefer and Jakob, 2006) and make detours that lead them away from or even out of sight of a reward (e.g. Tarsitano and Jackson, 1997, Tarsitano and Jackson, 1994). They readily associate colours with a reward (Jakob et al., 2007), as well as aversive stimuli (Nakamura and Yamashita, 2000), even following a reversal-learning protocol (Liedtke and Schneider, 2014). Jumping spiders also show developmental plasticity (West-Eberhard, 2003), because an enrichment of their rearing environment affects their response to prey and behavior in open-field and detour-tests (Carducci and Jakob, 2000). With vision as their primary sensory modality, jumping spiders’ intraspecific signalling strategies are dominated by visual displays, like the rising and waving of legs or pedipalps and also larger bodyparts (Jackson et al., 1990).

I carried out the following study with jumping spiders of the genus *Marpissa muscosa* (Clerck 1757). *M. muscosa*’s size ranges from 6 to 11 mm, featuring strong, darkish annulated legs and a body in mottled brown and grey with a camouflage-pattern on the opisthosoma. The prosoma of the adult females is marked by a distinct orange mask underneath the anterio-median eyes, whereas the males have enlarged pedipalps after reaching adulthood. In nature, *Marpissa* is often found in sunny spots on the bark of trees or wooden posts, where they, excellently disguised, look out for prey. They also build silken shelters they return to at night and thus are ideal for the study of memory based navigation and learning.

In this experiment I used jumping spiders that were raised under different conditions in the laboratory. I tested the *Marpissa* specimen on 7 consecutive days in a 4-armed maze to investigate their learning behavior. The maze contained a reward and a visual predictor of it, both of which changed their location after day 4 for a test on reversal learning.

Each individual took part in only one trial per day, to see if *Marpissa muscosa* is capable of retaining a memory for at least 24 hours.

I suppose that the tested specimen in general do not randomly choose which zone of the maze they visit first. My hypothesis is, they visit the reward-containing goal-zone first in trials following the discovery of the reward.

With “snapshot-navigation” and capabilities for generalizing, jumping spiders could be able to translate a bird’s eye view into a pedestrian perspective. So if *Marpissa* is given the opportunity to inspect the maze, including the reward and its predictor, from above, it will likely have an influence on its navigational behavior inside the maze, namely in 2 ways:

These “Streetview-Spiders” learn the new reward-location after the reversal on day 4 more quickly than individuals who were not allowed to inspect the maze from above.

“Streetview-Spiders” visit the reward earlier during a trial, independent from whether their first choice of goal-zone was correct or not.

My study does not provide a concluding answer on the question if spiders make use of abstract, allocentric representations of their surroundings, but offers general insight on how spiders build up spatial memories over time and in dependence from preceding visual exploration.

Materials and Methods

Materials

For the learning trials I used 3 wooden mazes with the following specifications:

Side lengths 15cm x 9,5cm, height of walls 1,5cm, 4 arms or “goal-zones” labelled A,B,C and D, respectively.

The mazes were coated in grey spraying varnish for a uniformly even surface texture as well as easier cleaning, and equipped with laminated paper markings at the first junction to facilitate visual differentiation of the left and right side. Just outside each goal-zone, a so called „transition-zone“ was marked with 2 lines for consistent designation of a spiders’ arrival and departure by the observer. A spider remaining in this transition-zone for at least 15 seconds was either determined as “still inside” when it came out of the goal-zone and likewise as “not inside” when it went there from outside a goal-zone. For a schematic drawing of the maze with measures see **Figure 1**.

I used a white, plastic screw cap as a starting area and handling-aid for the spiders, one half covered with a piece of plastic for shelter. This device will be referred to from here on as “starting cap”.

3 non-reflecting panes of glass, measuring 12cm x17cm each, served as see-through cover for the mazes.

The reward offered in each trial was a drop of 20µl of sugar water (2 cubes of sugar dissolved in 11ml Aq. dest.), because many spider species are known to accept nectar as a dietary addition (Jackson et al., 2001). An associative stimulus as the rewards’ predictor was provided in the form of a yellow Lego brick. The sugar water was substituted with a fresh load if the storage-container was visibly contaminated with dust or mold, as was the case in trial week 5.

All trials were recorded using a Panasonic HC-V500 cam-corder, video-analysis was conducted with VLC media-player (Version 2.0.6 Twoflower) and an according LUA-plugin named “spiderlab”, written by my colleague Daniel Redekop. The data was prepared, sorted and visualized for a general view using MS Office Excel2010, tests for data distribution and first exploratory analyses were done using IBM SPSS statistics 21. Further analyses, linear modeling and graph-creation employed R version 3.0.3 including the non-default packages car, lattice, lme4 and plyr. The following tutorials and guidelines regarding the proper usage of R and creation of generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) were utilized: Bolker et al., 2009; Crawley, 2011; Wikibooks, 2013; Zuur et al., 2009.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of the 4-armed maze with goal-zones labelled A,B,C and D. Differently marked branchings of the primary junction are labelled L (left) and R (right). For the use of transition-zones see text.

Definition of success and voluntary choice

A success was scored by a spider, when it chose to visit the reward-containing goal-zone first of all other zones. As the maze consisted of 4 arms, they had a chance of 25% to choose correctly. This measure of success was used, because the spiders visited the correct zone first and immediately drank from the reward only rarely during the preliminary case-study (less than 5 times in 56 trials). As it turned out in this study, trials with a successful first choice of zone in combination with drinking from the reward at all occurred at a comparable rate (see **Results**)

. This count includes bigger delays between sighting of and touching the reward as well, so it does not necessarily also mean the spider drank from the reward immediately after its discovery. Due to these reasons, the formerly success-criterion (correct choice + touch of reward) was changed (correct choice only) as explained above. It has to be noted, that it was only counted as drinking from the reward, when the spiders touched the drop of sugar water clearly with either both its front legs or chelicerae. Accidental touches that, for instance, occurred through failed climbing attempts or stumbling, were not measured.

Test subjects

Jumping spiders of the genus *Marpissa Muscosa* (N = 60), that were born in captivity and are first-generation offspring of spiders caught in the surroundings of Hamburg. All individuals were either sub-adult or mature when the trials took place. The spiders were kept under constant environmental

conditions with a day-length of 17 hours (light from 5:00 AM to 10:00 PM), a temperature of 26° C and a relative air humidity of 60%.

The spiders were raised in 2 cohorts under 3 different rearing conditions or treatment, respectively: deprived or **d**, group or **g**, physically enriched or **p**. The 2 cohorts differed in the age, in which the animals were transferred to the final treatment-cages. For **cohort 1**, the spiders were allocated to a treatment directly after hatching and in **cohort 2** the spiderlings remained in a group with up to 28 of their siblings, until they were allocated to a rearing condition and transferred to their final cages after about 2 months. Most of the tested spiders belonged to cohort 1, only the families with IDs beginning on A, 12 and 28B were raised in cohort 2, family 28A/B in the group treatment was a mixture of both cohorts. The rearing-condition treatments differed in the size of the cages, the cages' equipment and the number of specimen living in the same cage or the possibility to establish visual contact with their neighbours, respectively. The spiders were randomly allocated to each treatment, but the group-size was checked and adjusted for equality. The cages were clear plastic boxes of 2 different sizes with a detachable lid and up to 2 ventilation slits covered by plastic mesh, one slit for the smaller boxes, 2 slits for the bigger ones. The cages' size was also dependent from the rearing-condition treatment the spider was allocated to (see **Table 1**). In the deprived and enriched treatment, the individual boxes were separated in view from each other, so that no visual contact between the animals could be established. The cages for the group treatment contained no additional equipment and differed for adult specimen from the deprived treatment only in the possibility to see and visually engage neighbours, younger specimen were kept together in groups of up to 15 individuals inside boxes of size 2. Novel objects were put exclusively into the boxes of the enriched treatment to offer a more diverse environment. The objects' positions in the cage were changed in irregular intervals for all spiders in the enriched treatment. All of the animals were kept under the according conditions up until and during the experiments. Folded pieces of white adsorbent paper served as litter in all of the boxes and were regularly exchanged for clean paper during feeding sessions.

Table 1: cage size, equipment and social environment for the 3 different rearing-condition treatments.

rearing-condition treatment	cage size	additional equipment and social environment
Deprived	Size 1 (98x58x35mm)	None , no visual contact
Group	Size 2 (145x110x68mm) until adulthood, then individually Size 1 (98x58x35mm)	Size 2: Other <i>Marpissa</i> individuals Size 1: None, visual contact possible
Enriched	Size 2 (145x110x68mm)	New objects introduced weekly (see Appendix Table 9), no visual contact

The spiders usually were fed fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster* and *D. hydei*) once per week on Mondays, and the amount of food was adjusted for the age of the individual (see **Appendix**) to provide equal growth conditions for all spiders, independent of other rearing-conditions and treatments. All of the tested spiders were between 53 and 56 weeks old when the trials took place and thus old enough to follow a feeding protocol of 15 fruit flies per week. During the trials, the amount of food was not reduced for the individuals to reduce the risk of starvation, which was due to the uncertain foraging successes or acceptance of the reward during the experiments. Thus, up to 6 flies were given each, every second or third day during the trials, depending on how many flies were remaining in the spiders' cage. The latter 2 points most likely had an effect on the overall motivation of the spiders, as they probably were not hungry enough to willingly look for and feed from the reward (see **Discussion**)

The tested spiders were on average 60.3 ± 2.01 weeks old when they participated in the experiment and the age between the individuals differed by less than 10%.

Experimental procedures

The 60 individuals were equally split by rearing-conditions into 2 different exploration-treatment groups for comparison (from here on, the term “treatment” refers to this rather than the rearing conditions, which will be mentioned specifically as such). The t-treatment (t = transparent) was separated from the maze by a pane of clear glass, so that they were able to look down through it into the maze. The o-treatment (o = opaque) was separated from the maze by a piece of cardboard acting as a blindfold. Of the formerly chosen 60 individuals only 51 individuals remained for testing, because 9 of them died either shortly before trials started, during the first weeks of trials before it was their turn, or, in 2 cases, even after the individuals’ trials had started. 2 more individuals were left out in the analysis, because one spider did not participate in the given task on all trial days except for one (Spider-ID: AG1), and the other individual was left out, because of severe procedural errors made by the experimenter (Spider-ID: A30, inconsistently mixed up reward-locations and L/R-markings). The composition of actually tested individuals per treatment is shown in **Table 2**. Before the trials, the spiders were introduced and habituated to sugar water as a food source on 2 occasions, where animals were put into a petri-dish arena together with a drop of clear sugar solution. The actual learning-trials were conducted between August 31st and November 17th 2013.

The trials took place in a windowless underground room and the mazes were put on the same desk in the same compass alignment in each trial. This method was chosen to give the spiders the possibility to memorize the visual cues, which were provided by the ceiling of the room and to use them for orientation. In contrast to that, the maze-order of the 3 rearing conditions was randomized for each trial day anew to prevent me from associating a certain position in the video with a certain rearing-condition during the following analysis. The videos were recorded from about 50cm above the desks surface.

Table 2: Number of tested individuals and observations per treatment and rearing conditions.

rearing-conditions	treatment		Σ	observations
	opaque	transparent		
deprived	8	8	16	96
group	7	8	15	95
physically enriched	8	10	18	118
Σ	23	26	49	Σ
observations	147	162	Σ	309

Every day of testing consisted of 2 sessions of simultaneous trials: Up to 3 mazes were recorded in one session, the first trials started around noon-time (11:00AM - 1:30PM), the second turn started in the afternoon (2:00PM - 4:30PM). Each single trial consisted of 2 stages: 20 Minutes of exploration-time from above, which means, the spiders were allowed to move around on top of the maze, differing in glass-treatment.

Directly after the exploration part, delayed by up to 5 minutes (i.e. to catch escapees and take notes on trial-specifics), I started the video-recording again and put the starting caps, which contained a spider each, into the maze for 60 minutes.

One corner was equipped with a drop of 20 μ l sugar water as unconditioned food stimulus or reward, and next to it, a yellow Lego brick (size: 2 studs) as a conditioned stimulus, to enable association

between the stimuli and a memorization of the reward-location. Yellow was chosen, because it contrasted well with the walls of the maze through a pane of glass, combined with the relative brightness of the color compared to other accessible brick types. The reward was placed inside the maze before the exploration part started.

Every spider was tested on 7 consecutive days (see **Table 3**). On the first 4 days, the reward was placed in a previously chosen, random goal-zone, each day the same. On day 5 of testing and for the other remaining 2 days, the reward was placed into a new, also formerly chosen location, to possibly induce reverse learning. When I allocated the reward-location to the trials, the goal-zone position was chosen randomly between the session-groups of 3 spiders by lot. I also made sure that for every session-group the location was the same, which reduced the chance for experimenter-errors during trial set-up.

Table 3: Sample testing procedure for an individual experiment. The reversal trial takes place between day 4 and 5 and is indicated by a change of the exemplary reward location.

trial day	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
reward zone	A	A	A	A	C	C	C

After each trial, every maze and pane of glass was swiped clean with alcohol, also to remove any olfactorial cues the spider might have left. The boxes I used as an escape-countermeasure during the exploration part of the trial had their walls coated with petrol jelly to keep the spiders from climbing them. The ceiling was left uncoated for better visibility on video, which led to the rare case of finding a spider being stuck there upside down, because of a somersault that had catapulted it there and an avoidance of treading on jelly-coated areas, as the spiders were also repeatedly seen cleansing their tarsi after contact with the jelly.

Analyses

I conducted general linear mixed models (GLMM) fitted by Laplace approximation, to analyze possible influences of the treatment and length of the experiment on the spiders success chance. In this model, the ID of individual spiders was defined as a random factor to correct for repeated measurements. The dependent variable was the correct or incorrect response of the spiders which had a binomial error-structure and used the loglink function in R (version 3.03). The maximum model contained the following explanatory variables: 1) rearing conditions with the levels d, g and p, 2) glass-treatment with the levels o and t, 3) the trial number ranging from 1 to 7, and 4) the logarithmised delay between sight and touch as a motivation-proxy. This variable was logarithmised due to the wide range of values it could adopt, since it was measured in seconds from the start of the 1 hour trial. Two interactions were included: 5) Motivation : glass treatment and 6) rearing condition : glass treatment. No further interactions were included for the sake of avoiding over-complication and the loss of degrees of freedom. Also, the combination of the different structures or scales of measure of the explanatory variables would have made an interpretation and distinction of their specific influences more difficult than the scope of the experiment asked for. The full model was reduced step-by-step, starting with the least significant interaction. After this, the main effects were removed from the model until only significant variables remained. I compared the models with a χ^2 -Anova to check for significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between a model containing the focus variable and another model having it removed. The p-values from these analyses are found on the tables in the chapter **Results**.

Since other maze-experiments with jumping spiders employed more than 7 consecutive trials per individual (Jakob et al., 2007), or showed individually different performances in reversal learning tasks (Liedtke and Schneider, 2014), 2 types of GLMM regarding the response of the spiders were

made. The first type used the actually measured response data, including the reversal (“**Erf_rev**” in results). The second type was a hypothetical experiment, where the reward was considered to not have changed position in the reversal trial, so that the location of the goal-zone remained the same for all trial days (“**Erf_567**” in results). I used this approach post-hoc to see, whether the spiders would have performed differently without a reversal and if the compared glass-treatments changed their direction of influence on the success-chance. The results of this hypothetical experiment have to be considered with caution though, because they do not reflect the actual conditions the spiders were tested in, which is especially important considering the visual exploration before each trial: Of course, the spiders in the transparent glass-treatment were able to see where the reward really was and behave accordingly, regardless of the later assumed reward-location.

Results

Assessment of trial comparability and animals choice preferences

The allocation of reward-zones, or BEs, between all individuals was checked for an even distribution with a χ^2 -test ($\chi^2 = 0.0541$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.9967$, R version 3.03), even though the numbers of occurrences for single BEs were very similar already to the bare eye (A = 89, B = 86, C = 88 or D = 88, respectively).

To assess the possibility, that the results of the learning experiment were skewed by a side- or corner-preference in *Marpissa muscosa* on a population level, the number of first choices on the first trial-day was compared between corners (A = 10, B = 9, C = 17, D = 11) with a χ^2 -test. No deviation from an equal distribution was found ($\chi^2 = 3.2979$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.3479$, R version 3.03).

Descriptive statistics

49 Spiders tested on 7 consecutive days led to a number of $N = 343$ observations. Those 343 were reduced to 309 by the decision to discard the trial days preceding the discovery of the reward, a usual procedure for learning or memorization tasks involving a reward. For the reversal trial that meant counting trial number 1 from the first day the individual had visited the reward-zone, but had to keep day 5, when the reversal took place, at that position, so that a consistent trial number remained associated with this specific event. Obviously this procedure created a gap in the trial numbers, as was the case for 19 Individuals. For the hypothetical **experiment without reversal**, trial-numbers were counted consecutively from the first day of reward-discovery on. Accordingly, a spider took part in 6.306 ± 1.211 trials on average, regarding both experiments.

Spiders chose correctly in 61 of 309 trials on a whole in the reversal experiment, which leads to an overall success-ratio of 0.197 and is below the assumed level of chance of 0.25. Individuals in the opaque glass-treatment chose correctly 19 out of 147 times (SR = 0.129) and spiders in the transparent treatment scored successfully 42 out of 162 times (SR = 0.259). As for the no-reversal experiment, spiders chose correctly in 82 of the 309 cases, leading to an overall success-ratio of 0.265, which is just above the threshold of random choice. Here, the individuals in the opaque glass-treatment chose correctly 31 times (SR = 0.211) and spiders in the transparent treatment scored successfully 51 times (SR = 0.247). Such low success-ratios justified the abandonment of a binomial-test to see whether the spiders had performed better than expected by random chance. In 102 of the 309 trials in both experiments, spiders drank from the reward. To demonstrate the adequacy of changing the success-criterion (as mentioned on page 10) the following numbers are given for consideration: A spider scored a success and also drank from the reward in only 29 trials of the reversal experiment. In the no-reversal experiment, only 23 trials occurred with the combination of correct choice and reward touch.

It took all spiders on average 611.4 ± 468 seconds from the beginning of the trial to choose and visit the first goal-zone. Opaque spiders had a mean delay to first zone-choice of 615.8 ± 445.1 seconds, transparent spiders took on average 594.7 ± 492.4 for their first zone-choice.

The first sight contact to the reward was established at a mean of 1084.4 ± 845.3 seconds for all spiders. Opaque spiders took on average 1246 ± 907.6 seconds to discover the reward and transparent spiders 938.8 ± 759.9 seconds. A similar, but time-independent measurement, is the first occurrence of the reward location in the pathing-string (see "BE1_Stelle" in the **Glossary**). The average position of the first reward-visit was 5.141 ± 8.743 for all spiders. The mean position of the first reward-visit was

7.267 ± 11.289 for individuals in the opaque treatment and 3.223 ± 4.832 for individuals in the transparent treatment.

Structure of the derived GLMMs and influences on success-chance

Reversal experiment

The most parsimonious model of the ones containing the sight-touch delay (motivation) included only the explanatory factor motivation. No influence on the model was detected with the two interactions, glass-treatment, trial-number or the rearing condition. The result from the ANOVA-comparisons of models are shown in **Table 4**. The influence of the continuous motivation-proxy variable had to be manually investigated by prompting the predict-function in R. The output demonstrated a higher success-chance for trials with a bigger delay between sight and touch of the reward. This finding is especially pronounced in the spiders of the transparent-treatment and can be seen in **Figure 2**. The highest numbers for predicted chances to score a success were only to be found in the transparent treatment.

Table 4: Variables of the GLMM for the reversal experiment (GLMM: binomial error structure, loglink function) fitted by Laplace approximation for the response of spiders in each trial (correct or incorrect), including motivation-proxy. The maximum model was reduced until only significant variables remained in the final model. The table shows χ^2 , DF and p-values of each variable by the time it was excluded from the model. The sample numbers for this model were: Subject-IDs = 40, observations = 102

response	random factor	explanatory variable	χ^2	DF	p-Values
Erf_rev	Sp_ID	rearing condition	0.2569	2	0.8795
		glass treatment	1.4787	1	0.224
		trial number	1.7466	1	0.1863
		motivation***	185.95	1	< 0.0001
		motivation : glass treatment	1.3881	1	0.2387
		rearing condition : glass treatment	1.0194	2	0.6007

Of the models, that excluded the motivation proxy and thus had a bigger dataset, the least complex GLMM contained trial number and glass treatment (see **Table 5**). An inspection of the log-linked intercept-estimates showed a higher success-chance for the transparent treatment. The influence of the continuous trial-number variable on a spider's success chance was predicted to be negative with increasing trial number.

Table 5: Variables of the GLMM for the reversal experiment, excluding motivation-proxy. The table shows χ^2 , DF and p-values of each variable by the time it was excluded from the model. The sample numbers for this model were: Subject-IDs = 40, observations = 309

response	random factor	explanatory variable	χ^2	DF	p-Values
Erf_rev	Sp_ID	rearing condition	0.7313	2	0.6937
		glass treatment*	3.9215	1	0.04767
		trial number*	4.152	1	0.04159
		rearing condition : glass treatment	3.2245	2	0.1994

Figure 2: Boxplot of the success-failure dynamic between glass-treatment and the logarithmized motivation-proxy for the reversal experiment. N = 102 observations in 49 spiders.

Figure 3: Boxplot showing the relative frequency of successes for both glass-treatments in the reversal-experiment. The horizontal line at 0.25 represents the level of random chance for a correct choice. N = 309 observations in 49 spiders.

Figure 4: Progression of relative success-frequency with trial-number in the reversal experiment. While opaque spiders always remain below the threshold for random chance, transparent spiders have an increased success-ratio up until the reversal trial. Both treatments show a decline in success-ratio after the reversal, dropping to a comparably low level. N = 309 observations in 49 spiders.

No-reversal experiment

In the hypothetical no-reversal experiment, the most parsimonious model including the motivation-proxy featured the explanatory variables trial-number and the interaction of motivation and glass-treatment. Since terms of a significant interaction have to remain in the model during reduction, no further comparisons of influence took place for the single, uncombined variable (see **Table 6**). The predict-function again showed an increased chance of success for higher trial-numbers and another link between long motivation-delays and higher success-chance, as it was the case for the reversal-experiment without the interaction. As shown in **Figure 5**, this time there was a difference between the two glass-treatments: Opaque spiders demonstrated a smaller delay between sight and touch of the reward when they chose correctly and transparent spiders again showed a big delay when scoring a success.

Table 6: Variables of the GLMM for the no-reversal experiment, including motivation-proxy. The table shows χ^2 , DF and p-values of each variable by the time it was excluded from the model. The sample numbers for this model were: Subject-IDs = 49, observations = 102

response	random factor	explanatory variable	χ^2	DF	p-Values
Erf_567	Sp_ID	rearing condition	0.0457	2	0.9774
		glass treatment	--	--	--
		trial number*	6.281	1	0.0122
		motivation	--	--	--
		motivation : glass treatment*	5.0603	1	0.02448
		rearing condition : glass treatment	0.483	2	0.7854

In the no-reversal experiment excluding the motivation proxy, the final GLMM only contained the trial number as explanatory variable (see **Table 7**). Again, the influence of the continuous trial-number variable on a spider's success chance was predicted to be positive with increasing trial number. A trend towards significant difference ($p = 0.09408$) was observed for the comparison between a model including the glass-treatment and another model that did not. However, this difference was not sufficient enough to justify a transfer of that variable into the most parsimonious model.

Table 7: Variables of the GLMM for the no-reversal experiment, excluding motivation-proxy. The table shows χ^2 , DF and p-values of each variable by the time it was excluded from the model. The sample numbers for this model were: Subject-IDs = 49, observations = 309

response	random factor	explanatory variable	χ^2	DF	p-Values
Erf_567	Sp_ID	rearing condition	2.4754	2	0.29
		glass treatment ^x	2.8031	1	0.09408
		trial number***	29.806	1	< 0.0001
		rearing condition : glass treatment	1.5325	2	0.4648

Figure 5: Boxplot of the success-failure dynamic between glass-treatment and the logarithmized motivation-proxy for the no-reversal experiment. N = 102 observations in 49 spiders.

Figure 6: Boxplot showing the relative frequency of successes for both glass-treatments in the no-reversal experiment. The horizontal line at 0.25 represents the level of random chance for a correct choice. The success-ratio for the transparent treatment has increased to just above the threshold of random choice compared to Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.. N = 309 observations in 49 spiders.

Figure 7: Progression of relative success-frequency with trial-number in the no-reversal experiment. Again, transparent spiders show a higher relative success-frequency for the first 4 trial days than the opaque spiders. After day 4, when the reversal took place in the actual experiment, the success-ratios for transparent and opaque are inverted, with the opaque spiders scoring higher than before. Trial days 5, 6 and 7 show an increased success-ratio compared to the reversal-experiment as displayed in Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.. N = 309 observations in 49 spiders.

The difference in the overall success-ratios between the reversal and no-reversal experiment was investigated in R with a Wilcoxon-signed-rank test and found to be significant ($p = 0.0144$, $V = 440.5$). As the steep decline in success-ratio after day 4 in the reversal experiment is absent in the no-reversal experiment, the latter is inferred to have a higher overall success-ratio (compare **Figure 4** to **Figure 7**).

Comparisons of first zone-choice and first reward-discovery between glass-treatments

The individual means of all spiders belonging to a certain glass-treatment ($N_o = 23$, $N_t = 26$) were compared with a Mann-Whitney U-test (a subspecies of the Wilcoxon rank sum test in R) to see, if the opportunity to visually explore the maze from above had an influence on the time, the spiders took to enter either any goal-zone, or the reward-location for the first time during a trial.

For the time [seconds from the trial-start] the spiders took to make their first zone-choice, no significant difference was found between the opaque and transparent treatment ($W = 326$, $p = 0.5955$, see **Figure 8**).

Figure 8: Boxplot for the time of first entry into a goal-zone for the different glass-treatments.

The time the spiders took to enter the reward-containing zone, differed significantly between both glass-treatments, independently of the measure that was chosen for comparison: For the time in seconds from trial start, the p-value was 0.0372 ($W = 403.5$) and for the number of the first occurrence of the reward-location in the pathing-string (see **Glossary**) p was 0.03988 ($W = 402$). Spiders, that were able to visually explore before the trial, were quicker to enter the reward location regardless of their first, possibly wrong choice of goal-zone (see **Figure 9** and **Figure 10**).

Figure 9: Boxplot for the time of first entry into the reward-containing goal-zone for the different glass-treatments. Spiders of the transparent treatment are quicker.

Figure 10: Boxplot for the first occurrence of the reward-containing goal-zone in the pathing-string for the different glass-treatments. Spiders of the transparent treatment visited the reward at an earlier point in the sequence of all zone-visits.

Discussion

The 4-armed-maze experiment with *Marpissa muscosa* showed a rising success-chance with an increasing number of subsequent trials for the no reversal-experiment and a generally higher success-ratio for individuals that were allowed to inspect the maze from above before on-foot exploration. For the reversal experiment, a declining success-ratio with increasing number of subsequent trials was found. Even if the overall-performance of the spiders was low, the reported improvement over time in the no reversal-experiment supports the hypothesis, that *M. muscosa* is able to retain and recover newly formed spatial memories for more than 24 hours, since the individual animals were only tested once per day. This conclusion fits the results of the learning study with the jumping spider *Phidippus princeps* conducted by Jakob et al (2007), where spiders were tested once per day in an association-task and started to show evidence for learning-behavior only after more than 4 subsequent trials. They also assume that a period of one day is a realistic time-frame for encountering the same food-source again, with which I agree, given the complex foraging behavior and dietary diversity many jumping spiders demonstrate. Since the occurrence and abundance of special prey-items can be associated with distinct cues (biotic, like some types of prey being found only on certain plants, and abiotic, like different levels of light-exposure, humidity and temperature being linked to activity levels of prey), learning and re-learning of such associations might have an adaptive value in a foraging context (Liedtke and Schneider, 2014), especially in terms of avoiding costs for going to the wrong place and finding no or only unpalatable food there (Skow and Jakob, 2006).

I interpret the decrease in success-ratio in the reversal-experiment as a disability for reversal learning. The spiders of either glass-treatment were not able to memorize the location of the reward in the given time. 4 or 3 trials after the reversal, respectively, are not sufficient for laboratory-reared spiders to form a reliable memory and use it for navigation.

The increase of success-ratios in the no-reversal experiment can be interpreted as a reinforcement of learned associations through repetition (Rock, 1957; Anderson, 2000). Looking at the sudden increase of success-ratio after trial-day 4 in **Figure 7**, this is particularly apparent for spiders in the opaque-treatment, as they had no chance to assess the maze's layout (i.e. the reward-location) before on-foot exploration. Explorative activity, especially when coupled with locomotion and the resulting proprioceptive cues the animal gathers from it, is very important for successful navigation in space, as Benhamou et al. (1995) stresses it for mammals. In humans, a higher memory-acquisition of spatial features is linked to the opportunity to visually explore a virtual space by own actions and decisions, compared to passively watching a film or a series of snapshots that retraces a route through the experimental maze (Péruch et al., 1995).

Tarsitano and Jackson (1994; 1997) showed, that jumping spiders of different species are able to make detours that temporarily even lead them away from, or out of sight of the prey. This is an important hint on the ability to form and recall short-term memories of the environment for making navigational choices, as it is required in a maze. In another study (Tarsitano and Andrew, 1999), jumping spiders were observed to “scan” their environment before they started to move and stopped in regular intervals along their route to gather visual information anew so they could adapt their path if necessary. The way that this scanning-behavior was described, fits my own observations: *Marpissa* often stopped in front of a branching in the maze and turned around, sometimes several times while tilting its prosoma (to look up), before it walked any further. The same was also observed when a spider was about to enter one of the four goal-locations.

The result of the no-reversal experiment also puts into question, if the opaque spiders were employing a win-stay-loose-shift strategy (Posch, 1999), as the reward was not present anymore in the former

reward-location and they still often chose to firstly visit this goal-zone. The sudden drop of success-ratio for opaque spiders on day 7 though, could indicate that *M. muscosa* only shifts strategies after a couple of wrong, unrewarded outcomes. Regarding the cyclic nature of many biological phenomena, this might be advantageous for individuals that lack other means of gathering information about their environment, specifically if the path to the target remains unobstructed over several check-ups and thus puts no additional strain on the animals' energy budget through increased locomotor activity. The locomotor activity does not seem to be such an important restraining factor in the well-fed test spiders, taking into account how persistently some specimen were observed to pace between adjacent goal-zones (see below in **General notes on the behavior of *Marpissa muscosa***). I go into more detail there, but it is possible that this 'pacing' is either a manifestation of frustration, an inappropriate random search pattern (colloquially anthropomorphing, I would call that spider either stupid, silly or undecided). Another possibility is, that this behavior serves to either update and verify, and then consolidate the memory of the topological information of the environment, i.e. the accessibility of the different zones and their spatial relations to each other (Alvernhe et al., 2012; Poucet and Herrmann, 2001).

As it is difficult to infer rather abstract, mental processes from the mere observation of externally manifested behavior, so these results do not provide a final answer to the question if jumping spiders, or arthropods in general, use decentralized "cognitive maps" (sensu Tolman, 1948, as proposed by Gould in 1986 for bees) either. There is still much discussion on this topic (e.g. Bennett, 1996; Cruse and Wehner, 2011; Gallistel, 1998, 2008; Collett and Collett, 2002; Freksa and Mark, 1999; Redish, 1999), but innovative and frugal explanatory models for space navigation (Dongqing Shi et al., 2013; Möller et al., 2013; Shatkay, 1998) or cooperative foraging strategies (Wagner, 2000) are derived from diverse experiments with artificial intelligences and autonomously deciding robots. In such systems, all environmental factors, but also the internal states and behavioral repertoires of the involved participants can be manipulated to gain insights about their influence on different performances or even directly fitness. For now, I am not aware of a study that analyzed robot-navigation and observed such repetitive pacing in their machines as I did with many spiders, but it would be interesting to know if such behavior occurs in robots, too. If that is the case, one could look for the mechanistic basics (in terms of software programming and hardware circuitry) in this experiment and compare it with some of the navigational algorithms and 'neuronal circuit-boards' that are exemplary proposed by e.g. Benhamou et al. (1995), Cruse and Wehner (2011), Giurfa (2013) and Martinet et al. (2011). Trullier et al. (1997) reviewed navigation strategies also in relation to robotics, but criticized the lack of capacity for detour and shortcutting behaviors in many models that claim to use "cognitive map"-like mechanisms. This constitutes an argument for jumping spiders employing a possibly allocentric map-like mental representation, if detouring and shortcutting is found in these animals.

The GLMMs including the motivation-proxy are difficult to interpret. In the reversal experiment (**Figure 2**), the delay between seeing and touching the reward did not differ for opaque spiders either being successful or failing. Transparent spiders were observed to have a higher delay when they had scored successfully, so they were not very motivated to drink from the sugar water but still visited the reward-location first. As they were seen to explore the maze further and, if at all, came back later to drink from the reward, their motivation for visiting the reward-zone first, might be due to "curiosity" (Loewenstein, 1994) to look for the predictor they had seen in the explorative part of the trial. The smaller and less varying delay for the opaque spiders in the no-reversal experiment (**Figure 5**) compared to the reversal-experiment (**Figure 2**) indicates motivation to drink from the sugar water, as well as some sort of a surprise-moment. They had visited the old reward-location first and found nothing to be there after the reversal. When they explored the rest of the maze and suddenly came

across the reward in the new location, they often drank from it right after its discovery as if they were looking for it. This is an example for how different motivation or “drive” (Reznikova, 2007) plays out as realized behavior in dependence from the environmental and inner circumstances, here: 1) having the opportunity to explore the environment blindly and surprisingly finding food or memorizing its location, respectively, or 2) having the opportunity to check up on a conspicuous stimulus that was seen from above before an actual on-foot exploration can both be sufficiently rewarding for an animal by themselves. This ‘curiosity hypothesis’ is backed up by the significant differences for the first zone-visit or first reward-visit comparisons between the glass-treatments (see **Figure 9** and **Figure 10**). The spiders in the transparent treatment visited the reward earlier than the opaque spiders, in a less varying, smaller period of time. Since there was no significant difference found in the time the spiders in the different glass-treatments took to first visit any zone (**Figure 8**), the transparent spiders must have been motivated to search for the predictor.

As I already mentioned in *Analyses* the results of the hypothetical no reversal-experiment have to be considered with care, because the spiders might have behaved differently if the reward really had not changed location.

The spiders used in my study showed a very low performance compared to the study of Liedtke (2014), in which only spiders caught in the wild were tested. After all, spiders raised under controlled but unnatural and generally deprived conditions might have lacked incentives to employ and improve their cognitive abilities. They never were forced to change nesting site due to environmental changes or to search over longer distances for their own, diverse food in an environment presenting a whole range of multimodal stimuli, they were supplied regularly with everything they needed for survival. This could be very important for the success of such experiments, since Jackson and Carter (2001) have found, that the jumping spider *Portia labiata* showed a lower level of reliance on trial-and-error learning strategies when their parents or grandparents came from a population inhabiting an environment with low prey diversity.

It also has to be taken into account that Liedtke (2014) tested the spiders in an only 2-armed T-maze, so that a 4-armed maze might be just on the boundary of what *Marpissa* is capable of under experimental conditions. Jumping spiders that were born in the wild and then caught for experimentation perform a lot better in several tasks they are tested for, according to personal communication with Liedtke. He also found first hints on sex-dependent differences in the performances of the animals in the ongoing analyses. This is a factor I have not taken into account this far and it would be interesting to reanalyse the data with sex as another random factor. In conclusion, a lot of insight on the influence of generally deprived rearing conditions could be gained, if a 4-armed maze experiment similar to mine would be conducted with jumping spiders caught in the wild.

I consider the unfortunate combination of laboratory-reared spiders, possibly unattractive reward, the spiders’ probably low motivation and the complexity of the presented task were responsible for the observed results. Nevertheless, it was shown that preceding visual exploration seems to have an influence on the navigational accuracy of *M. muscosa*, which is a positive result, standing for itself.

With the results of this experiment, it still is not known, if jumping spiders are able to make use of a decentralized, conceptual map as humans can (with a piece of colorfully printed paper), but apparently they are able to translate a birds’ eye view into a pedestrians perspective, so the title “Spider Streetview” seems to be justified.

Error sources

The transport and handling of the spiders before the start of each trial presumably excited the animals greatly, so that a resting period of about 10 minutes might not have been enough to calm them down again. This could explain why some individuals did not leave the starting-cap for ten minutes or more after starting the exploration-part of the trial. They also were handled with a brush between the trial-phases and again, some specimen remained inside the sheltering starting cap for a long time, in 5 cases 30 minutes or more. It should be noted, that there seemed to be individual, as well as daily differences in excitability, which could be a promising prospect for personality studies.

I took great care during the video-analysis not to overlook any zone-transitions of the spiders, but it is still possible that I missed some transitions after the first choice and reward-visit, due to environmental distractions from sound or movement or even my own blinking. This error-rate could be assessed through repeated analyses by different people and a following comparison between the results. My tutor and I considered this procedure, but decided it was impractical for scheduling reasons. Also, it would have been a possibility to count all zone-transitions with an added time-mark of the video, but I considered it to be unnecessary data-generation since the experiment was less about the accurate path a spider took than the time-frame of its first choice and reward-visit

The association between predictor (Lego-brick) and food-stimulus could have been very weak, because the reward was freely accessible for the spiders and not given to them immediately after a correct zone-choice. That means that even if the spider chose correctly, it did not necessarily get rewarded and thus had no chance to form a direct association between the 2 stimuli. A living or at least moving prey-item probably would have been a better choice as a reward. Fruit-flies or small mealworms are highly mobile and so small, that it is difficult to restrain their movement without risk of injury or death from over-exhaustion, so I chose a reward that may not be a typical food-item for *Marpissa muscosa* but stays in the same place over the whole trial.

The decision to use sugar water as a reward was made, because nectarivory was shown to be a widespread foraging strategy in jumping spiders (Jackson et al., 2001). It is unclear though, if the reward was attractive enough compared to live prey or might have been even repulsive for some individuals (already before changing it due to contamination), since some animals repeatedly fell into the droplet or accidentally dipped one leg into it and jerked, or quickly backed away from it to start cleaning movements. I deem it very possible, that stickiness is an aversive stimulus for spiders regardless of taste, as the bristles and fine hairs on their bodies are sensory organs that probably perform worse when clogged. Unfamiliarity with the reward can be ruled out, because all specimen were found to have tasted the sugar water at least once in the preliminary sugar water habituation trials. As the amount of usual food (*Drosophila* sp.) for the spiders was not reduced during the maze-trials, the spiders' motivation to actively search for, and drink from the reward may have been low and reward-touches mainly due to the sheer curiosity of the animals.

I already mentioned, that little is known about key-stimuli for *M. muscosa*, which might be relevant for knowing which types of visual patterns are readily distinguished by this species. I am referring to this, because of the possibility that the first branch-markings for the floor of the left and right side of the maze were not recognized as landmarks, or navigational cues, respectively. It is unclear if the spiders perceived and associated those markings with the topography of the maze at all, or if they rather used other environmental cues as navigational aid, like the ceiling or the positions of the camera and light sources.

Another possible influence on the results may be found in the circumstance, that many tested spiders were recently found to be infested with parasitic mites. So far, no quantitative measure of the spiders'

parasitic load was recorded, so that the potential effect of said parasitism on the spiders' performance remains unclear. Since it is known from vertebrates, that mite-infestation influences oxygen-consumption, body-mass as well as grooming and resting behavior (Giorgi et al., 2001), it is likely that arthropods are negatively affected by parasitic mites as well, especially considering their comparably smaller body-size.

General notes on the behavior of *Marpissa muscosa*

Repetitive pacing and probing of walls

The spiders sometimes repeatedly went from one goal-zone to the neighbouring one on the same side of the maze (A and D or B and C), often for several minutes in a row. While they were doing this, I saw them probing the crevasse between maze-wall and glass-cover with their front legs, apparently looking for a way to escape. This persistent, repetitive behavior could be a sign of frustration (Mason and Rushen, 2008) with the confined freedom of movement, as the spiders were seen pacing along and probing mainly at the outer margins of the maze. Another possible interpretation of this stereotypic behavior is an inappropriate search-pattern in the spiders, since they did not just walk along all the walls, which would get the animal to visit the whole maze after some time and, at last, to find the reward. Instead, they stopped in one corner, turned around and paced back along the same wall, also after they had already found the reward. As this behavior was not quantified, it is unclear if it is typical for the species on a whole, something only jumping spiders held in captivity do, or if the specific rearing conditions, or glass-treatments, respectively, were facilitating this behavior.

Line of sight and walking on the ceiling

I often noticed the spiders climbing the ceiling of the maze very early after the beginning of a trial. They had problems keeping a grip on the non-reflecting glass, since their tarsi slid towards the center of their bodies as they were pulled down by gravity. They also regularly stuck down a drop-line to the ceiling's surface, in which they often got entangled when falling down. I assume that they were not able to make use of their flexible pedicels for looking around in such situations, as I saw them moving or inclining their prosoma to direct their gaze only when they were walking on the floor of the maze. As they spent a lot of time walking upside down or trying to climb the ceiling again, it is doubtful if they were able to see the drop of sugar water at all from this position. On the other hand, the animals in the transparent treatment were seen to readily gaze down through the glass during the exploration part of the trial, apparently scanning what was below them. This is consistent with another observed behavior, which is climbing a vantage point in their cages and looking around in all directions, aligning their body with movements in their surroundings, especially movements of prey-items. Some individuals stayed sitting on the wall closest to the camera, staring upwards for prolonged bouts of time, if at all, only moving their pedipalps or front legs or probing the wall and glass. Taking into account their acute sense of vision with focal points of 30cm distance or more, it is likely, that *Marpissa* spotted the reflection of the camera lens or the light that indicates 'recording in progress'. Such sources of distraction might have had an influence on the animals' participation in the task, as they might have been more interested in these views than searching for the reward. As jumping spiders can distinguish between conspecifics and prey-insects over a distance of at least 30 cm (Harland et al., 1999), and considering that pedipalp- or leg-waving seem to be important behaviors in jumping spider communication (Jackson et al., 1990), it is possible, that the specimens mistook the spider eye-like cues of the camera lens for a conspecific and tried to evoke a response from it. An answer to this question though, would demand more research on jumping spiders' key stimuli and communication behaviors.

Remarkable orientation and memory in one certain specimen?

There is one special incidence I would like to finally share, even if it is just anecdotal and thus has no evidentiary value whatsoever. The specimen with the ID 39-13, an adult female belonging to the deprived rearing condition and opaque glass-treatment, escaped on its first day of experimentation during the exploration part of the trial. I wasn't able to find it again, even after I repeatedly had checked the several pieces of equipment, the table, its underside and the carpet, that unluckily employed a grey salt-and-pepper pattern, which supposedly masks *M. muscosa* very well. I also checked behind parts of the walls' serrated paneling that had served to muffle echoes when the room was still used as a sound-recording studio. So I booked the specimen as "lost" after 2 days and continued the experiment with the other remaining individuals that were scheduled for that week. On day 3 after its escape, I came into the experimentation room again and noticed a dark spot in the white plastic tray for the mazes, already before I had turned on the light. As it turned out, it was the lost spider, sitting very exposed in the middle of the tray. From my tutors and my own former experiences, this was quite unexpected, as *M. muscosa* usually hides in cracks or only lurks in open, well-lit places that provide a certain amount of camouflage in texture and color, like the bark of trees, forest litter or weathered wood. The humidity in the room was low and there were probably not many sources of food, so specimen 39-13 was lucky to be found again. As remarkable as this little field trip was, it didn't seem to have an influence on the individuals' performance in the maze one week later: It only scored 2 successes in the last of 6 counted trials, and those were most certainly due to the spiders search pattern. It had mostly paced for the first 4 days between the 2 right zones, A and D. After the reversal trial, the reward was in zone A, so the spider eventually found it, still pacing on the right side. Only afterwards, this individual started to explore the rest of the maze. As the opportunity to manipulate the environment or get a look at a scene seems to be incentive enough for some highly cognitive vertebrates (Butler, 1953), this behavior begs the question, if incentives or rewards stimulate explorative behavior in spiders as well.

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Acknowledgements

My gratitude goes towards the whole Ethology working group at the University of Hamburg. I'd like to especially thank Prof. Dr. Jutta Schneider, who gave me the opportunity to write my thesis on such an interesting topic under the guidance of so many open-minded and supportive people. I am very grateful, that she and Dr. Wiebke Schuett are willing to correct and evaluate my work, which already benefitted strongly from their advice. I also need to give thanks to my tutor Jannis Liedtke, who helped me to work out the key aspects of my questions and focus on them, but on the other hand was never reluctant to discuss new and possibly even spider-unrelated ideas regarding cognition, learning and navigation. Geli and Tomma, our technical assistants, were also a great help when it came to the practical side of experimentation: You always know where to find things, and if not, you have an idea where to look for it or what alternatives to use. We all would be flat on our backs if it weren't for you!

Furthermore, I have to express my gratitude towards my colleagues Daniel Redekop and Anna-Lena Krügel. Daniel helped Jannis and me to take care of the spiders and generously allowed me to use a revised version of his self-made program for easier video-analysis. Anna-Lena stood by my side with plenty of advice for writing, access to her private library and a patient ear when the frustration hit hard. Of course, thanks go out to my friends and family as well: You did a splendid job in supporting me during the whole time, even if it was only by listening and bearing either my lengthy stand-up lectures about *Marpissa*'s behavior and explanations of more technical biology terms, or by just cooking a nice meal and offering a hug.

Last but not least, I also like to give special thanks to my test subjects, who endured the whole endeavor in the name of science. The work with you taught me to see, that it is the right thing to do, to follow one's own amazement when it comes to finding a personal field of research. Also, your big eyes, your well perceivable shifts of attention and the communicative efforts with your pedipalps make it difficult not to like you, you rock!

Statement of original contribution

I hereby declare to have composed this paper single handedly and that I have used no other resources than referred to in text and references. I have not submitted this work to any other examination procedure. The submitted print version corresponds to the copy on the electronic storage device. I agree on the work being published.

Appendix

Glossary and abbreviations for variables and their definitions in text and data-sheets

The abbreviations come from German terms but are explained in English. The German term is given as well, if possible in a few words and in case the meaning is directly related to the letters used for abbreviation.

Anz_A/_B/_C/_D: One-trial count of visits to the corner with the name given in the variables' title (A, B, C or D respectively).

ABCD_vis: Count of different zones the spiders visited during the according trial. Has a theoretical minimum of 0 when the spider does not participate and only remains in the starting zone and a maximum of 4 when all different corners were visited during the same trial.

BE: „Eckzone mit Belohnung“ = goal-zone or corner containing the reward.

Erf: „Erfolg“ = Success, spiders chooses the correct goal-zone first. Given as Y/N response per trial (J = yes, N = no). The measure of successes was used to determine the success-ratio of the spiders under the hypothetical assumption that spiders which had memorized or seen the location of reward-placement, always went there first before visiting other corners.

Erf_rev: Modified criterion for success on the 5th trial day when the reward location was changed. In this data-column, the spider was counted as successful on day 5 (“reverse learning”) when it had first approached the goal-zone that *formerly* contained the reward.

Erf_567: Same as for **Erf_rev**, but extended to all of the last 3 trial-days (days 5, 6 and 7). This was used to determine the success-ratio of the spiders, independent from the reversal-learning task under the hypothetical assumption, that the reward location did not change on day 5.

BB: „Belohnungs-Berührung“ = Touching of reward. The spider must be actively drinking from or approach the reward with its cheliceres, accidental stumbling or falling into reward was not counted. The moment of first touch is given in seconds after trial-start and the touch-duration measured. Subsequent touches were only recorded in number.

BV = Number of visits to the rewarded goal-zone (Belohnung = **B**) during one trial.

BV1 or **1BV** = The first trial-day on which the spider visited and saw the reward. Also used as a modifier for table-headers, indicating that trial-numbers were counted based on this variable, not when the first trial really was conducted. The point in time for the reversal trial was marked with day 5, regardless of preceding participation. If a spider discovered the reward only after the reversal, then that day was labeled as trial 1 and counted consecutively from there on.

Example: If a spider discovered the reward on the very first trial day, nothing changed and trial-numbers were counted consecutively from 1 to 7. If a spider first saw the reward on day 3, this day is counted as the first day of trials for the according individual and the former 2 days are discarded, so the trial numbers are counted 1, 2, 5, 6, 7. If another spider first

discovered the reward on day 6, there were only 2 trials for the according individual, namely trial number 1 and 2.

EQ or **SR**, respectively = “**Erfolgs-Quotient**”, which means **success-ratio**. A ratio or quotient consisting of the number of achieved successes or correct choices, divided by the number of participated trials.

Example: If a spider chose correctly 3 of 7 times, its overall SR is $3/7$ or 0.42857.

Glas: 2 different types of exploration-treatment, o = opaque, t = transparent (see

Materials and Methods)

Pfad = Path. The pathing-sequence of visited goal-zones as a string of characters consisting of the letters A, B, C and D.

Example: ADADBBCAD.

BE1_stelle = Number of the position at which the **BE** is firstly observed in „**Pfad**“. Example: if the pathing-sequence is CBCBACBBCADA and the reward is found in A, it first occurs at position 5.

LR_Pfad = Pathing-sequence of visited goal-zones coded for **L**eft and **R**ight side of the maze. In relation to the first-branch markings (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**), corners A and D were defined as right, B and C as left.

SB: „**B**elohnungs-**S**ichtkontakt“ = First line-of-sight contact with reward after trial-start. Either measured when spider enters BE for the first time or aligns its antero-median eyes to the reward while being inbetween the 2 lines of the transition zone. Given in seconds after trial-start.

SBB_dif = Timelag between **SB** and **BB** given in seconds. Was chosen as a likely indicator for subjects' motivation (see Liedtke and Schneider, 2014), but the results begged a different interpretation.

Treatment: 3 different types of rearing-conditions of the spiders, d = deprived, g = group, p = physically enriched.

VWoche: Number of trial week, 1-10.

W1: „1. **W**ahl“ = 1st choice of a side (left or right) or goal-zone (ABCD). Given in seconds after trial-start. Criteria for application are given with the specifically referenced abbreviations that follow.

W1_LR = 1st entry into one of the differently marked primary branchings (**L**eft or **R**ight). Only applies, if either the spider crossed the marked zone completely and entered a goal-zone, or, if the spider remained with its prosoma in or behind the marked zone for at least 15 seconds.

W1_Eck = 1st entry into one of the 4 goal-zones. Only applies, if spider remains with the prosoma inside the corner (= **Eck**) and behind the 2nd line of the marked transition-zone for at least 15 seconds.

Zone-vis: Count of all visited zones during one trial, given as integer.

L-vis/R-vis: One-trial count of visited zones on the left or right side, respectively.

ZWT: „**Z**uckerwasser-**T**ropfen“ = Drop of sugar water.

Table 8: Age-dependant feeding protocol for *Marpissa muscosa*. "F" stands for flying *Drosophila*, "W" for walking specimen, which differ from each other in size.

Lower age limit	Number of weekly fed
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(in weeks)	Drosophila flies
1	Monday 2 F, Friday 2 F
3	3 W
10	5 W
15	6 W
18	7 W
23	10 W
26	13 W
32	15 W

Table 9: Schedule for the placement of additional novel objects into cages of the enriched treatment.

object	Time of introduction to cohort 1	Time of introduction to cohort 2
piece of bark	day 1	day 1
2 pebbles	day 1	day 1
Iceland moss	day 2	day 1
step-bench, plywood	day 3	day 1
colored Lego-brick	week 10	week 4
dried Oak-leaf	week 12	week 4
piece of string, orange	week 21	week 21
crown cork	week 46	week 46